

The New Notation for Hyperoperation of a Sequence

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Abstract

For a sequence $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$, we define the exponent, tetration and pentation of a sequence a_n as $\overset{n}{\mathbb{E}}(a_k) = a_1[3]a_2[3] \cdots [3]a_n$, $\overset{n}{\mathbb{T}}(a_k) = a_1[4]a_2[4] \cdots [4]a_n$, $\overset{n}{\mathbb{P}}(a_k) = a_1[5]a_2[5] \cdots [5]a_n$. Also, we define the i -th hyperoperation of a sequence a_n as $\overset{n}{\mathbb{H}}_i(a_k) = a_1[i]a_2[i] \cdots [i]a_n$.

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Introduction

In this paper, we provide the notation for hyperoperations of a sequence. This notation will make it easier to write hyperoperations of sequence that are very long, and difficult to write.

Definition

The notation for summation and product of sequence a_n is already defined as

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (a_k) = a_1[1]a_2[1] \cdots [1]a_n = a_1 + a_2 + \cdots + a_n \quad [1]$$

$$\prod_{k=1}^n (a_k) = a_1[2]a_2[2] \cdots [2]a_n = a_1 a_2 \cdots a_n \quad [2]$$

using the uppercase of σ , and π because the first letter of ‘summation’, and ‘product’ corresponds to σ , and π .

Now, we will define the new notations for exponent, tetration, pentation, and hyperoperation of sequence a_n by the same way as a Capital-sigma notation and Capital-pi notation.

For a sequence $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$, we define the notation for exponent of a sequence a_n as

$$\overset{n}{\text{E}}(a_k) = a_1[3]a_2[3] \cdots [3]a_n = a_1 \uparrow a_2 \uparrow \cdots \uparrow a_n$$

using the uppercase of ε because the first letter of ‘exponent’ corresponds to ε .

Also, we define the notation for tetration and pentation of a sequence a_n as

$$\overset{n}{\text{T}}(a_k) = a_1[4]a_2[4] \cdots [4]a_n = a_1 \uparrow\uparrow a_2 \uparrow\uparrow \cdots \uparrow\uparrow a_n$$

$$\overset{n}{\text{P}}(a_k) = a_1[5]a_2[5] \cdots [5]a_n = a_1 \uparrow^3 a_2 \uparrow^3 \cdots \uparrow^3 a_n$$

using the uppercase of τ , and ϕ because the first letter of ‘tetration’, and ‘pentation’ corresponds to τ , and ϕ .

Moreover, we define the notation for i -th hyperoperation of a sequence a_n as

$$\overset{n}{\text{H}}_i(a_k) = a_1[i]a_2[i] \cdots [i]a_n$$

using the uppercase of η because the first letter of ‘hyperoperation’ corresponds to uppercase of η .

Examples

- (1) $\overset{4}{\underset{k=1}{\text{E}}}(2k) = 2 \uparrow 4 \uparrow 6 \uparrow 8 = 2^{4^{6^8}}$
- (2) $\overset{3}{\underset{k=1}{\text{T}}}(k-4)^2 = 9 \uparrow\uparrow 4 \uparrow\uparrow 1 = 9^{9^{9^9}}$
- (3) $\overset{n}{\underset{k=1}{\text{H}}}_1(k) = \sum_{k=1}^n k = 1 + 2 + \dots + n = \frac{1}{2}n(n+1)$
- (4) $\overset{n}{\underset{k=1}{\text{H}}}_2(k) = \prod_{k=1}^n k = 1 \times 2 \times \dots \times n = n!$

Conclusion

In this paper, we provided the new notation for hyperoperation of a sequence. We defined the exponent, tetration, and pentation of a sequence a_n as $\overset{n}{\underset{k=1}{\text{E}}}(a_k) = a_1[3]a_2[3] \cdots [3]a_n$, $\overset{n}{\underset{k=1}{\text{T}}}(a_k) = a_1[4]a_2[4] \cdots [4]a_n$, $\overset{n}{\underset{k=1}{\text{P}}}(a_k) = a_1[5]a_2[5] \cdots [5]a_n$ for a sequence $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$. Also, we defined the i -th hyperoperation of a sequence a_n as $\overset{n}{\underset{k=1}{\text{H}}}_i(a_k) = a_1[i]a_2[i] \cdots [i]a_n$ for a sequence $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$.

Reference

- [1] “[Summation](#)”. wikipedia.com. Last edited on 6 January 2022.
- [2] “[Multiplication](#)”. wikipedia.com. Last edited on 30 January 2022.